

Effect of heat treatment on the vertical bond strength of 3D printed CF-PEEK composite implants

S. Pilehvar^{1*}, R. Heidari¹, and H. Mozaffari-Jovein^{1,2}

¹ Institute of Materials Science and Engineering, Furtwangen University Campus Tuttlingen, Germany

² Department of Microsystems Technology, University of Freiburg, Germany

* Corresponding author, email: soheil.pilehvar@hs-furtwangen.de

Abstract: Polyetheretherketone (PEEK) composites are increasingly used in biomedical applications due to their mechanical strength, biocompatibility and imaging behaviour. In order to use PEEK as a load-bearing implant, its mechanical properties must be optimised. This study investigates the effect of annealing on 3D printed PEEK and carbon fibre reinforced PEEK (CF-PEEK) samples. The results show that annealing improves crystal uniformity and overall sample quality, highlighting its potential to improve PEEK composites for use in orthopaedic and spinal implants.

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I. Introduction

Polyetheretherketone (PEEK) polymer composites are gaining increasing attention due to their good mechanical properties. These composites offer excellent stability in sterilization processes and have excellent biocompatibility. In addition, these composites are a radiolucent material and do not produce artifacts during post-operative evaluation on X-ray, computed tomography (CT), or magnetic resonance imaging (MRI), which are disadvantages of metallic implants. A potential disadvantage is that PEEK alone is neither osteogenic nor bioactive. Conventionally manufactured tectonic polyether composites are therefore increasingly being used as biomaterials for orthopedic, trauma, and spinal implants [1,2].

II. Material and methods

Two different types of filaments were used in the present work. The PEEK filament (TECAFIL PEEK VX natural - 1.75 mm) is supplied by Ensinger plastics (Germany) with a density of 1.32 g/cm³, a glass transition temperature of 143°C, an average molecular weight of 115,000 g/mol and a melting temperature of 343°C. TECAFIL PEEK VX natural is an unfilled PEEK filament based on Victrex® PEEK 450 and CF-PEEK filament (TECAFIL PEEK VX CF30 Black - 1.75 mm) supplied by Ensinger plastics (Germany) with a density of 1.38 g/cm³, an average molecular weight of 115,000 g/mol. TECAFIL PEEK VX CF30 Black carbon felt PEEK filament is a material based on Victrex® PEEK 450.

Once the parts were manufactured, the process of "heat treatment" was carried out to grow crystals and improve interlayer penetration. To fill the existing knowledge gap, a comprehensive and benchmark study was conducted to investigate the therapeutic effect and the change in

properties of the extruded fibres under different conditions. The starting filaments were extruded on an Intamsys Funmat HT Enhanced printer. Analysis of the fired and extruded filaments provided a better understanding of the effect of different printing conditions on the quality of the printed products. The parts produced were then annealed.

These approaches allow a more accurate evaluation of the printing process and provide valuable insights for optimizing part properties. Tensile tests were performed on 3D-printed PEEK and CF-PEEK parts with and without annealing at room temperature in accordance with relevant standards. Tensile tests were performed in accordance with ISO 527-2 using a ZwickRoell machine with a 50 kN load cell. The test specimens were loaded in the Z-direction at a strain rate of 5 mm/min to measure strength and elongation and 1 mm/min to measure the modulus of elasticity.

Figure 1: Graphical illustration of the results from the tensile tests in Z-direction for different PEEK conditions

Table 1: Tensile test results for PEEK and CF-PEEK samples

Z-direction	Tensile strength [MPa]	Strain [%]
CF-PEEK	57,6	1,2
CF-PEEK An*	61,1	1,5
PEEK	6,77	-
PEEK An	10,5	-

*An: Annealed

III. Results and discussion

Figure 1 and Table 1 clearly show that the addition of carbon fibres leads to a significant improvement in mechanical properties compared to pure PEEK and brings them closer to the properties of bone cortex. The strength in the Z-direction has increased due to the interlocking and penetration of additional layers by the increase in surface roughness due to the carbon fibres, and in almost all cases the mechanical properties can be influenced by subsequent heat treatment. This is due to the increased content of crystalline material. The lower tensile strength values for pure PEEK in the Z-direction can be explained by the strong crystal growth behaviour, which reduces the mechanical anchoring between the layers.

IV. Conclusions

In this work, PEEK and CF-PEEK samples were printed in Z-orientation using the annealing process and the normal process (without annealing). By using this process, a more uniform crystal distribution and coherence enhancing diffusion was achieved and the overall quality of our printed samples was improved.

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